

HOW TO TEACH ENGLISH LANGUAGE AS A TARGET LANGUAGE AT SCHOOL

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Abstract: This article describes effective methods and approaches that aimed to instruct children to learn English language as a target language. Also, here is pointed out the major issues which teachers come across during teaching process.

Key words: method, approach target language, issues, teaching process.

Annotatsiya: Bu maqolada Ingliz tilini bolalarga o‘rgatishni maqsad qiluvchi ba’zi samarali metodlar va usullar haqida so‘z boradi. Hamda, o‘qituvchilar o‘qitish jarayonida duch keladigan ba’zi muammolarni aytishni lozim topdik.

Kalit so‘zlar: metod, usul, o‘rganilayotgan til, muammo, o‘qitish jarayoni.

INTRODUCTION

In today's process of globalization, the effect of the radical reform of the education system of Uzbekistan is evident in all areas related to this area. The state pays special attention to the teaching and further development of foreign languages in the education system, which is a key sector of socio-economic, political and cultural life of the country, one of the vital factors that directly affect the morale of the population. at the policy level⁷. By the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev on May 6, 2021 on measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages, the problems in the system were analyzed in detail and priorities were identified⁸.

“President of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov signed a resolution “On measures on further improving system of studying foreign language” on 10 December 2012. The document was adopted to improve teaching foreign languages, training specialists with good language skills, introducing advanced technologies into education system. According to resolution, foreign languages, predominantly English language, will be

⁷ Югай Е. 2021. Цифровая культура и общество: проблемы их взаимоотношений в условиях глобализации. Общество и инновации. 2, 7/5 (авг. 2021), 58–67.

DOI:<https://doi.org/10.47689/2181-1415-vol2-iss7/S-pp58-67>.

⁸CURRENT RESEARCH JOURNAL OF HISTORY 2(6): 43-48, June 2021 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.37547/history-crjh-02-06-10> ISSN 2767-472X ©2021 Master Journals

taught in all schools of Uzbekistan from first classes as game plays. From the second class, the alphabet, reading and grammar will be taught⁹.

DISCUSSION

As the matter of fact, it is considered that teaching and learning English language is the main attribute of our education system in Uzbekistan¹⁰. There are lots of methods and approaches introduced to our education system in order to teach effectively in schools. Does learning a second language have lots of benefits for children? Definitely! It helps them develop better critical thinking and problem-solving skills and boosts memory and concentration skills, among many, many more. But how to teach English as a second language? That ones a little more tricky.

It can be a daunting task thinking about how to teach the English language to non-English learners. Regardless of class size or ability level, helping children to learn a new language comes with many challenges. You'll have to have a lot of patience (just like every teacher out there), especially as every child learns differently and at a different pace, which only increases the challenge. But helping children develop their confidence in speaking and using another language can also be extremely rewarding. And you can check out our hopefully handy tips on how to teach the English language below to give you a helping hand¹¹.

METHODS

Nowadays teachers are utilizing the following methods to teach English language effectively in classes.

Use lots of visuals. Images are great for supporting learning. A child may not understand that the word ‘pencil’ means pencil, but they recognize what a picture of a pencil is. By combining text with images, children will be able to better develop their understanding. And pictures also add some color to your classroom, making it more interesting and a better learning environment. To do this, you could use some brilliant ESL classroom display resources.

Keep it simple. This is especially important when dealing with beginners. Try to keep sentences simple so that learners can develop their knowledge, and then you can build on it. You could, for example, ensure their understanding of simple instructions that you'll be using in class. These could be things like ‘stop and listen’ or ‘put your pens down’. These short but informative requests are much simpler to understand than ‘can everybody please stop what they’re doing and listen’, or ‘stop your writing and put your pens down onto the table’.

Mix it up. Learning in just one way quickly leads to children becoming disinterested, disengaged, and disgusted (just kidding, but I couldn’t think of another

⁹Tashkent, Uzbekistan (UzDaily.com)

¹⁰ Yugay Evgeniya Viktorovna. (2022). INFORMATION AND DIGITAL LITERACY: THEIR CONCEPTS AND SKILLS. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6945140>

¹¹<https://www.twinkl.co.in/blog/20-tips-on-how-to-teach-a-child-english-as-a-second-language>

‘dis’ to add). By using different formats for learning, whether that be worksheets, games or Power Points, learners will stay stimulated. We know it can be time-consuming to create all of these resources, but a helping hand from Twinkle and our array of teaching tools could help to make your teaching life easier.

Use technology. Technology has quickly become man’s best friend over the recent years, and it should become a teacher’s best friend, too! Technology is a great way to get children engaged in a lesson. With so many apps, interactive games and platforms out there, there’s lots for a teacher to choose from to use in their lessons, just like these brilliant interactive games ¹².

CONCLUSION

All in all, teaching English language is being one of the developing branches of the education system of Uzbekistan nowadays. As the result of creating such opportunities, even some rural areas of our country have great facilities to teach and learn foreign languages. The Ministry of Education is taking more actions to improve the students’ textbooks and workbooks at schools including modern technologies at classes in order to increase the quality of foreign language teaching process.

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¹² YUGAY E. V. DIGITAL CULTURE AND ITS INFLUENCE ON VALUE ASPECTS OF HUMAN BEING //THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука. – 2021. – №. 12. – С. 422-425.

